

ANALYSIS OF THEORETICAL VIEWS ON STABLE COMBINATIONS AND THEIR TYPES

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Abstract. *Today it is no secret that phraseological units are studied as an important area of linguistics, and that linguistic scientists have been interested and researched in this area even at all times. The field of phraseology, phraseological units and their differences from stable compounds such as Proverbs, matals have become the subject of scientific research. In this article, the study of phraseological units, which are considered a type of stable compounds, in World linguistics, as well as a comprehensive observation of its methods and ways of analysis have been presented.*

Keywords: *phraseologism, phraseological unit, phraseological combination, word, phrase, syntactic construction, semantic meaning.*

As we know, phraseology is one of the largest sections of linguistics. To date, most linguists have studied phraseological units with different approaches. Phraseology is an area of linguistics that studies stable units, that is, it can be called the doctrine of phraseological units. In addition, if we look at this section with linguocultural view for analysis, phraseology manifests itself as a set of phraseological units of a particular language and nation. For example, the phraseology of Uzbek language, like the phraseology of English language.

If we analyze the word phraseology, literally the term “phraseology” means doctrine of speech turns, (Greek. Phrasis “oborot, expression”; logos “concept, doctrine”), nowadays the term has been restudied by scientists within linguistics, and in this science phraseology is a branch of linguistics that studies stable idiomatic units, that is can be called the doctrine of phraseological units.

Moreover, if we consider linguocultural phraseological units, then phraseology can be called a set of phraseological units of a particular language and nation (phraseology of Uzbek language, phraseology of English language). Relying on such ideas, we must realize that various scientists have come to the conclusion that its ambiguous content has survived to this day, based on various facts.

It is very difficult to accurately determine the range of their objects depending on the appearance and formation of phraseological units, since the components of idiomatic units are genetically and functionally different, have a different construction and are also different in meaning. Today, the complexity of a phenomenon can be demonstrated by terminological diversity in determining the concept of “phraseology”, as well as the structural components of the objects of phraseological units and their meanings.

The study of phraseology as a science in world linguistics. B. A. Larin believes that phraseology, as a linguistic discipline, is still in the stage of hidden development, as a mature fruit of preparatory work, is added to the body of philological sciences. A more complete definition is given by N. M. Shansky: “phraseology is the branch of language science that studies the phraseological system in its current state and historical development”.

In linguistics, relying on the above points, phraseological units are a very comprehensive field, and the term “phraseology” can be used in two senses – broad and narrow – and they are as follows:

- 1) the field of linguistics,
- 2) set of separate speech units. So A' is a set of phraseological units separated on the basis of the Z opposition.

A distinctive feature of such speech units is recognized as the sustainable nature of tilde application as ready-made integrated units as well as reproduction. There are many different views of scientists with a taste for phraseology but the most common term for the common name is given by academic V. V Vinogradov. It is him who introduced the term "phraseological unit" into science. The study of phraseological units has interested linguists at all times, and in world linguistics reflections about a phraseological unit was given by V. L. Arkhangelsky. He argues that “phraseological unity is a constant combination of verbal signs present in the language at this stage of historical development: marginal and holistic, which are repeated in the speech of its speakers; based on the internal dependence of members; consisting of at least two strictly defined units at the lexical level located inside, having a certain sequence; grammatically organized by existing models of phrases or sentences; has a single meaning of combined elements”.

In many cases, phraseological units in textbooks and scientific works, the aspect that distinguishes it from other language units, from words, and in a second way from phrases, is its stagnation. Thus, M. I. Fomina believes that “expressive”, the presence of a generalized-phraseological meaning, the constancy of the structural composition, phonetic diversity, two or more stresses “are differences of phraseological unity from the word. Full/partial meaning, the relative possibility of replacing/skipping one of their components while maintaining a common meaning, the unity of the syntactic functions of the entire phraseological unit” distinguishes it from the phrase.

In world linguistics, phraseological units have been extensively studied by Molotkova making other comments to phraseological units in her pamphlets “phraseologism and the word”, “phraseologism and the phrase”. There, “none of the categorical properties of phraseological unity are associated with a phrase”, “phraseological unity and a word have common features: lexical meaning and grammatical categories”.

Another example is the definitions of phraseological units. In world linguistics, according to A. M. Babkin, a phraseological unit is recognized as a semantic unit of a more complex order than a word, but is functionally close to a word and, accordingly, a member of a sentence, that is, a combination of words with a constant composition and characterized by semantic specificity. Phraseological units have the following signs:

- 1) semantic integrity,
- 2) stability,
- 3) the presence of a figurative value,
- 4) expressive-emotional expressiveness.

Many researchers note other characteristics as characteristic signs of phraseologism, and since such opposites define the nature of phraseological units, we will not dwell on any other definitions given to phraseological research in the works of linguists of different worlds.

In his book “stylistics of artistic speech”, the well-known linguistic scientist Evfimov describes phraseological views as follows: “under the phraseological composition of the language,

of course, there are clear, often repeated, stable, in the sense of word order, “winged” phrases that exist in the language and find the most diverse use in the work of art. Further, phraseological units in our language again may be in the following case: “phraseology usually begins where the free lexical meaning of the word is hidden by phraseological connection, when any phrase is repetitive, recognizable, “winged”, characterized by its figurative use.

Therefore, the phraseological tools of the language include not only phrases, but also, proverbs, aphorisms of writers, winged lines of poems, stable formulas and turns of a scientific and technical nature, stationery stamps, production and technical phrases, etc.

Russian linguist scientist in his book “the phraseology of the modern Russian language”, N. M. Shansky introduces into linguistics the concept of “phraseological revolution” and sufficiently illuminates the issue. In phraseological units, the integrity of meaning, the stability of structure and composition, in his opinion, distinguish phraseological units from free expressions. From the words of phraseological units, they are distinguished by their structure and composition, if words are formed from morphemes, phraseological units are formed from words. This treatise also gives to the linguistic scientist the definition, which should be considered a phraseological unit: “a phraseological revolution is a unit of language, formed from two or more stressed components of a verbal character, repeated in a ready – made form, determined by its meaning, composition, structure”.

The main types of phraseological units

In World linguistics as we have noted above, phraseological units have been studied in a very broad way and are cited with sufficient data bases. Academician A. A. Shakhmatov in his “syntax of the Russian language” under the decomposition of the phrase “not only for lexicology, but also for grammar”, wrote that “we understand the relationship of the components in its composition, the determination of the dominant and related elements. At the same time, it is also worth noting that the composition of some phrases cannot be broken down. So, for example, in terms of modern syntactic relations, the composition of two-component phrases does not break”.

The relationship of components in phrases the composition of which is not dissociated into parts can be explained from a historical point of view, but it is incomprehensible, immobile from the point of view of the living system of modern grammatical relations. Thus, A. Shakhmatov said that “the combination of a fixed word with a definition tends to compose a single speech in most cases; but in most cases, both members of the combination, of course, retain their independence due to their union with the corresponding words in addition to these combinations.

The issue of various forms of interaction and interdependence of lexical and grammatical phenomena within the framework of different phraseological groups has been studied and researched in detail by linguistic scientists. Russian scientist A. A. Shakhmatov distinguished four types of indivisible phrases from a syntactic point of view.

Phrases that are not understood in terms of grammatically inseparable, lively syntactic relations, but are completely lexically free, i.e. it is complemented by any oral material, dressed in appropriate forms.

The question of phraseological groups close to one in meaning has attracted the attention of many linguists. And yet, except for individual observations and some general judgments, the result of the semantic study of phraseological units is not noticeable. Research shows that within these topics, Sh.Balinese's book “Trait and stylistique francoursaise” covered these issues very

clearly. Like A.A.Shakhmatov, linguistic scientists research the bipolar type of phraseological groups or vocabulary:

1) the combination of words is individual, random and unstable; here the connection between parts of the phrase is broken down immediately after its formation, and the words that make up the group of words otherwise have complete freedom to merge;

2) phraseological speeches or phrases are regular, stable, in which words are in close contact to express some idea, one image, lose their independence, become inseparable and only gain meaning in the inseparable unity of the phrase.

If, in a group of words, each graphic unit loses part of its individual meaning or even a combination of these elements, does not preserve any phraseological unit, then the meaning of the whole will never be equal to the sum of the values of the elements. Such a phrase as *ants*, which comes from the exchange of words, means qualitatively new. The phraseological unit is characterized by its external and internal properties. External, formal signs do not play a conditional, deceptive, volatile and decisive role. These include a fixed word order and the impossibility of replacing any of the words that make up the phraseological unit with a synonym or other word. Internal signs of phraseological unity are not absolute, but singular, and include the following important signs: the ability to replace the combination of words with a single word that is meaningfully equivalent; forgetting the meaning of the constituent elements of a phrase, the semantic inseparability of speech to elements; its omonimical distance from relevant free combinations and phraseological unity in the sense of: *My brother-in-law and aunt cared for these flowers and animals as if they were the apples of their eyes.* (the phrase *apple of their eyes*, quoted in this example, is the presence of lexical, syntactic or semantic archaisms: the ability to produce a word for an entire phrase into a single complex word and sometimes the specificity of pronunciation)

Phraseological units come from phraseological groups. In phraseological groups, Bally defines some types not by their constructive characteristics, but by the specificity of lexical-semantic content.

These are, for example, phraseological groups, with reinforcing definitions such as: *diametrically opposed*, *categorically rejecting*, *bitter regret*, *great impression*, etc., or stable verb combinations with periphrases of simple verbs: *win – win*, *decide – make decisions*, *negotiate*. Bally breaks down comfortably in the transition stages from less related phraseological groups to absolute units, stating: “here it is even more difficult to distinguish between familiar groups and absolute units, but this difference is not so important”.

Obviously, a huge number of linguistic and semantic variations of phraseologisms are very easy and naturally distinguished – completely indivisible, inseparable types, the meaning of which is completely independent of the lexical composition, the meanings of their components, and differs from each other through words and signs.

Phraseological units of this type can be called phraseological compounds.

There is no connection, even potential, with their meaning and the value of their components. If their semantic elements are the same as some independent, separate words of the language, then their ratio is purely homonym.

Phraseological compounds can be etymologized. But this “folk etymology” does not explain their true semantic history or influence on their use.

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